

Minimum isolation distance for hybrid rice production

H. L. Sharma, H. Singh, and D. P. Joshi,
Seed Research and Production Unit,
Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana
141004, India

In studies to determine the minimum isolation distance for maintaining male sterile lines and for producing genetically pure hybrid rice seed, Zhen Shan 97A, a cytoplasmic-genic male sterile (CMS) line, was used as the female parent and Zhen Shan 97B as the pollinator. Zhen Shan 97B seedlings were transplanted at 40 d after seeding (DAS) on 19 and 26 Jul 1986 in a 5- × 5-m block. Zhen Shan 97A was transplanted in 50-m-long single rows in directions related to normal prevailing winds during anthesis. Plant-to-plant distance was 50 cm. Seed set was recorded by distance from pollinator. Percentage seed set was computed as the ratio of seeds/plant to florets/plant.

Seed set on CMS plants near the

Seed set on cytoplasmic male sterile rice plants. Ludhiana, India.

Distance (m) from pollinator	Percent seed set of plants at given direction from pollinator							
1	1.73	2.07	2.28	2.01	1.90	2.81	1.80	
5	0.79	0.57	0.63	0.68	0.51	0.89	0.35	
10	0.31	0.00	0.38	0.35	0.42	0.34	0.00	
14	0.10	0.18	0.19	0.00	0.39	0.00	0.11	
15	0.13	0.00	0.16	0.00	0.18	0.14	—	
16	0.11	0.12	0.00	0.31	0.35	0.18	—	
17	—	—	0.11	0.16	0.29	0.12	—	
18	—	—	0.14	0.15	0.34	—	—	
19	—	—	0.00	—	0.00	—	—	
20	—	—	0.00	—	0.18	—	—	
21	—	—	0.00	—	0.11	—	—	
22	—	—	0.12	—	—	—	—	
50	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	

pollinator was high, but dropped drastically as distance from pollinator increased. No seed set occurred beyond 22 m in any direction (see table). The maximum coverage occurred when average wind velocity was 4 km/h, mean temperature was 27.5 °C, and relative humidity was 74% during Sep 1986.

These results suggest that rice pollen can disperse up to about 22 m under

those particular weather conditions. However, because pollen dispersal depends upon such factors as pollination vigor, wind direction, wind velocity, relative humidity, temperature, and hours of sunshine, confirmation over years and locations is needed to establish isolation distances for maintaining male sterile lines and for producing hybrid seed. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization TISSUE CULTURE

Tissue culture propagation of cytosterile stocks

D.S. Kumari, N.P. Sarma, and G.J.N. Rao,
Central Rice Research Institute,
Cuttack 753006, India

Somatic embryogenesis through formation of myriad supernumerary and adventitious embryoids in callus cultures is an attractive approach for mass propagation of the cytosterile stocks used in hybrid rice production. Cytosterile stocks (A lines) are maintained by pollination with fertile isonuclear maintainers (B lines).

For large-scale multiplication, A and B lines normally are grown in alternating rows in isolation. We have successfully used tissue culture techniques to mass-produce four cytosterile lines possessing WA

cytoplasm: V20A, Madhu A, IR48483A, and IR46830A.

Callus was initiated from dehusked sterilized seeds by culturing on N6 medium supplemented with 2 mg 2,4-dichlorophenoxy acetic acid (2,4-D) per liter. Each seed embryo yielded a 400-500 mg callus mass within 3-4 wk.

The 4-wk-old embryo-derived calluses were transferred to MS regeneration medium containing auxin (naphthalene acetic acid [NAA], 0.75 mg/ liter), cytokinins (kinetin, 0.25 mg/ liter), and benzyladenine (BA) (0.75 mg/liter) in the proportion 3:1:3. Very high frequency plantlet regeneration was obtained within 3 wk; 200-250 plantlets could be regenerated from the callus derived from a single seed (see figure).

With another passage in culture, the callus derived from a single seed can

Plantlets obtained from somatic callus cultured from a single seed.

give rise to a tenfold increase in mass, and 2,000-3,000 regenerated plantlets